

Influence of Regional Wave Scatter Characteristics on Long-Term Sloshing Design Loads for LNG Cargo Tanks

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Abstract. This paper investigates the influence of wave scatter tables on the long-term approach for estimating sloshing design loads in LNG cargo tanks. Due to the nonlinear and highly stochastic nature of sloshing phenomena, model testing remains the most widely accepted method for deriving design loads. Traditionally, short-term analyses focusing on extreme wave conditions over a limited duration have been used to minimize the number of experimental conditions. However, such approaches often produce highly scattered results, especially under severe sea states, limiting their reliability and convergence. As a result, there is growing interest in long-term analysis frameworks that account for a wide range of sea states, including moderate but frequently occurring conditions, to reduce uncertainty and improve design robustness. In this study, long-term sloshing load assessments were conducted based on a comprehensive model test campaign using a 174K LNG carrier tank configuration. Two distinct wave scatter datasets were compared: the widely used North Atlantic (NA) scatter diagram and a global route-specific scatter constructed by integrating AIS-based LNG carrier trajectories with ERA5 hindcast wave data. The model test matrix was designed to cover major combinations of wave heights and periods with high sloshing relevance, allowing the probabilistic extrapolation of sloshing loads under each environmental condition. The results highlight the significant impact of regional wave characteristics on long-term sloshing load predictions. Notably, the global route-based scatter led to lower design loads compared to the NA scatter, illustrating the importance of using realistic operational wave statistics in sloshing assessments. These findings provide practical insights into the potential for optimized and cost-effective containment system designs tailored to actual service routes of LNG carriers.

Keywords: *Sloshing, long-term analysis, wave scatter table.*

1 Introduction

The global demand for cryogenic fuels and chemicals has been rapidly increasing, leading to a surge in liquefied natural gas (LNG) carrier construction and plans for new ammonia and liquid hydrogen transport vessels. Global LNG demand is predicted to increase by 60% by 2040 as countries move towards cleaner energy sources [1], [2], [3]. At the same time, ammonia and hydrogen are emerging as next-generation energy carriers that require transport at cryogenic conditions, and significant increases in ammonia shipping demand are expected. In this context, sloshing refers to the movement of liquid within a partially filled tank, which is an important factor in ship design. Sloshing can generate extreme impact pressures on the containment system of LNG and other cryogenic tanks, threatening structural integrity and safety if not properly accounted for. Thus, accurate sloshing analysis is of paramount importance to ensure the safe marine transportation of LNG and upcoming cryogenic cargoes like ammonia and hydrogen.

Traditionally, sloshing design has relied on a short-term approach that emphasizes extreme wave conditions. Classification society guidelines and early industry practices typically considered a single severe sea state, often defined as a 25-year return period condition over a 3-hour duration, to represent the worst-case sloshing scenario [4], [5], [6], [7]. Although most of these guidelines also provide recommendations for long-term assessment frameworks [5], [6], [7], [8], the practical application of such methods has remained limited due to the substantial computational burden and the complexity associated with evaluating a wide range of sea state conditions.

The short-term approach simplifies the analysis but has clear limitations. First, it neglects the contribution of less severe but more frequently occurring sea states. Experimental studies revealed that the largest sloshing pressures can occur in moderate sea states rather than the absolute extreme waves. Certain combinations of wave period, amplitude, and tank filling level can induce resonant fluid motion that leads to stronger impacts under

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milder sea conditions. Second, by focusing only on an overly conservative design storm, the short-term method may either under-predict the true worst-case impacts or over-design the structure without quantifying the actual risk. Recognizing these issues, researchers and engineers have increasingly turned toward long-term probabilistic sloshing assessment methods that consider a wide range of sea states encountered over the ship's lifetime [9], [10], [11]. Such long-term approaches accumulate the effects of both calm and rough weather, providing a statistical distribution of sloshing loads instead of a single deterministic value. Pioneering works have introduced reliability-based frameworks for sloshing load assessment, demonstrating the value of considering the full spectrum of sea conditions and their probabilities [12], [13]. As a result, modern design guidelines now increasingly favor long-term sloshing analysis or require justification if a short-term method is used, reflecting an industry shift toward more robust, probability-based design criteria [14], [15], [16].

A crucial element in any long-term sloshing analysis is the wave scatter data representing the environmental conditions the vessel will experience. The wave scatter table provides the joint probability distribution of sea states, typically characterized by significant wave height and mean wave period, for a given region or operational route. These probabilistic wave data directly influence the predicted sloshing loads, since ship motions are driven by wave conditions. In a long-term analysis, the sloshing model test results or simulations for each considered sea state must be weighted by the probability of that sea state's occurrence. An accurate wave scatter diagram is important for dependable sloshing load predictions, as biases or inaccuracies in the wave climate can affect design load estimation. If a vessel operates worldwide, a conservative scatter diagram such as the North Atlantic (NA) wave scatter is often assumed as a design basis [17]. However, many LNG ships have specific trading patterns or defined routes, and using a generic global extreme environment might be overly conservative. To address this, modern approaches incorporate regional or route-specific wave scatter data when available. Some class guidelines allow that if a ship's service area is restricted, a scatter diagram for that specific region can be used in the design assessment [6]. By tailoring the environmental input to the actual operating profile, one can obtain a more pertinent probabilistic load evaluation. Even mild sea states with large occurrence probability may contribute to long-term loads if they cause a particular sloshing resonance. Despite this recognition, a specific research gap remains: the *sensitivity* of long-term sloshing design loads to the *choice* of wave scatter diagram has rarely been quantified on a common experimental basis. In practice, NA or a single regional climatology is often used without (i) measuring the bias this choice introduces, (ii) constructing route-aware scatter directly from observed LNG trading patterns, and (iii) demonstrating the resulting impact on return-period design loads. Thus, the careful consideration of regional wave scatter data is essential as it ensures that the long-term sloshing load analysis accurately captures the vessel's true wave exposure.

This study investigates the effect of different wave scatter tables on the long-term sloshing load analysis in LNG cargo tanks. To address the identified gap, we explicitly quantify how long-term sloshing design loads change with the environmental input by comparing a standard NA scatter with a global, route-specific scatter constructed from observed LNG carrier trajectories and hindcast waves. The study investigates the effect of using route-specific wave climate data, instead of generic data, on the predicted impact pressures and probabilities of sloshing. The objectives of this study are twofold: (1) to derive global wave scatter data specifically tailored for LNG carriers and other cryogenic cargo vessels, and (2) to quantify the sensitivity of sloshing design loads to the choice of wave scatter input. To achieve these objectives, a long-term sloshing load assessment framework that integrates high-fidelity experimental data with realistic environmental statistics was essential. For this purpose, the recently developed *Unified Procedure of Sloshing Load Analysis for Korean Industries* [18] was adopted as the basis of the methodological approach. Using a comprehensive model-test database for a 174K LNG tank configuration, we perform probabilistic extrapolations under each sea state, weight by the competing scatter diagrams, and compare return-period sloshing pressures. This route-aware analysis provides direct, measurement-backed evidence of the design impact of environmental choice, clarifying when NA-based assumptions are over-conservative and by how much.

First, sloshing model tests have been conducted to measure impact pressures under a range of sea states and filling levels representative of real operations [9]. Rather than testing only an extreme condition, the experiments cover numerous conditions across the scatter diagram to build a broad database of sloshing responses. Since the experimental matrix sufficiently covers the range of wave heights and periods that can induce sloshing impacts under NA conditions, recognized as the most severe sea environment, the application of alternative scatter diagrams in the long-term analysis posed no difficulty. Based on the experimental database, the study investigates the long-term design sloshing loads corresponding to different wave scatter diagrams.

In addition to the widely used NA scatter diagram, this study also incorporates global wave scatter tables that reflect the actual trading routes of LNG and other cryogenic cargo vessels. To construct these route-specific scatter diagrams, AIS (Automatic Identification System) data from LNG carriers were utilized to identify representative operating routes and their associated sea state histories. These operational records were then coupled with long-

term hindcast data to derive detailed scatter tables that reflect the realistic wave conditions encountered by vessels over their service life. Finally, the study combines experimental sloshing load data with these route-specific scatter tables to perform a long-term probabilistic analysis. This integration allows us to estimate extreme sloshing pressures at given return periods and compare them with results using standard scatter diagrams. The findings highlight the significance of selecting appropriate wave climate data in sloshing assessments and demonstrate a route-aware methodology for more accurate and cost-effective LNG cargo containment system design.

2 Procedure of Sloshing Load Assessment

2.1 General Procedure

The overall flowchart of sloshing load assessment for LNG cargo tanks is illustrated in Figure 1 (adapted from Korean Register). Once the target vessel is selected and its cargo loading conditions are defined, seakeeping analysis is performed to simulate the ship's motions under various wave environments. These motion responses are then used as input to replicate tank motions in model tests, enabling the estimation of sloshing loads under each specified sea state.

During the model testing phase, a small-scale membrane-type tank partially filled with water is subjected to irregular multi-degree-of-freedom motions that represent the seaway conditions corresponding to either design or operational scenarios. Dynamic impact pressures on the inner walls of the tank are measured throughout the test using high-response pressure sensors. These measured pressures are post-processed to evaluate structural loads and extract relevant sloshing events. In this post-processing stage, time-domain pressure signals are converted into time histories of resultant loads over various loaded areas. A statistical treatment is then applied to extract pressure peaks and build probabilistic distribution of sloshing load. The estimated loads serve as the basis for structural strength assessments. A long-term probability distribution of sloshing load can be derived based on the probability distribution of every condition that the model test is performed. The long-term exceedance probability of sloshing load can be expressed as follows.

$$Q(x) = \sum_{i=1}^{NF} \sum_{j=1}^{NH} \sum_{k=1}^{NS} p_i p_j p_k \cdot \frac{R_{ijk}}{R} Q_{ijk}(x) \quad (1)$$

The long-term exceedance probability of sloshing loads is calculated as a weighted average of exceedance probabilities for all operational conditions, each defined by a combination of cargo filling level, wave heading, and sea state (wave height and period). The occurrence probabilities of these variables are denoted as p_i , p_j , and p_k respectively. The contribution of each condition is weighted by the joint probability $p_i \cdot p_j \cdot p_k$, and further scaled by the relative sloshing event rate, expressed as R_{ijk} / R . Here, R_{ijk} is the sloshing impact event rate measured from model testing under condition k , and R is the average event rate across all tested conditions. This weighting reflects not only how often a condition occurs, but also how frequently it generates significant sloshing loads, leading to a more realistic and physically meaningful estimation of long-term design sloshing pressures. As implied by the formulation, the sloshing load estimation process explicitly accounts for the occurrence probability of each combination of wave height and wave period. Consequently, the wave scatter diagram—which defines the statistical distribution of sea states—plays a critical role in determining the resulting long-term design sloshing loads. The accuracy and representativeness of this diagram directly influence the reliability of the load predictions. Therefore, for accurate evaluation of operationally relevant sloshing risks, it is critical to select a wave scatter table that reflects the actual design or service conditions of the vessel. While the IGC Code mandates the use of the North Atlantic scatter diagram as a standard design basis for LNG carriers, this requirement does not universally apply to all vessel types. For example, LNG bunkering vessels or other ships equipped with membrane-type containment systems but not classified under IGC may benefit from the use of more realistic, route-specific wave scatter data. In such cases, adopting an environment that aligns with the vessel's actual operational profile can lead to safer yet more efficient designs, avoiding excessive conservatism while maintaining structural integrity.

The structural evaluation framework for LNG containment systems is generally categorized into two levels: Level 1 and Level 2 assessments. Level 1 involves dynamic structural analysis in which the maximum sloshing loads, obtained from experiments or numerical simulations, are converted into equivalent static loads. These are then used to perform simplified verification of the containment system's strength. The present study focuses

primarily on the estimation of design sloshing loads and their application in Level 1 structural evaluation. As illustrated in the flowchart, the overall assessment procedure remains largely consistent regardless of whether a short-term or long-term approach is adopted. The key distinction between the two lies in how wave environments are considered and how design sloshing loads are derived. While the short-term method evaluates loads under a limited set of extreme sea conditions, the long-term approach incorporates a wide range of operational sea states and their associated probabilities. that this study does not extend to the structural verification process based on the derived sloshing loads, but rather focuses on the load estimation methodology itself

Figure 1. Flowchart of sloshing load and strength assessment on cargo containment system, Korean Register [6]

2.2 Acquisition of Long-Term Sloshing Model Test Dataset

In order to support a robust long-term sloshing load assessment, a comprehensive set of model test data was essential. This study utilized a high-fidelity experimental dataset produced through the series of *Joint Industrial Projects for Long-Term Sloshing Assessment*, coordinated by Seoul National University with participation from Korean Register, HD Hyundai Heavy Industries, Samsung Heavy Industries, and Hanwha Ocean. The dataset was specifically designed to cover a wide range of sea states and operational conditions relevant to probabilistic sloshing evaluation.

The experiments were conducted at a filling level corresponding to 95% of the tank height (assuming that the ship experience 40% of lifetime on full loading condition and no sloshing on upper section on ballast condition) and considered three relative wave headings: head sea (180°), diagonal sea (135°), and beam sea (90°). For each heading, a total of 129 wave conditions were commonly selected based on the North Atlantic (NA) wave scatter diagram, aiming to cover nearly all significant combinations of wave height and wave period. In addition, several test conditions were later added based on the preliminary results of the sloshing experiments to ensure sufficient coverage of influential scenarios.

As vessel speeds, ranging from 5 knots to the full-service speed of 19.5 knots, were applied according to the sea state and heading. For each test condition, model-scale data corresponding to at least 10 hours of full-scale operation were collected [9]. In conditions that were found to significantly influence the long-term sloshing load distribution, the acquisition time was extended up to 30 hours. The tested conditions, when mapped onto the NA scatter diagram, are highlighted in Figure 2, showing the extent of coverage across the sea state space. It should be noted that the representative North Atlantic wave scatter diagram was recently updated with the release of Revision 2 of IACS Recommendation No. 34 [19]. However, the sloshing model tests in this study were conducted prior to the publication of Rev.2. Therefore, the wave scatter diagram used in this research is based on the earlier version, Rev.1 of Rec.34. [20]

HS Tz	0.5	1.5	2.5	3.5	4.5	5.5	6.5	7.5	8.5	9.5	10.5	11.5	12.5	13.5	14.5	15.5	16.5	17.5	18.5	sum	
0.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3	133.7	865.6	1186.0	634.2	186.3	36.9	5.6	0.7	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3050.4	
1.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	29.3	986.0	4976.0	7738.0	5569.7	2375.7	703.5	160.7	30.5	5.1	0.8	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	22575.4	
2.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.2	197.5	2158.8	6230.0	7449.5	4860.4	2066.0	644.5	160.2	33.7	6.3	1.1	0.2	0.0	0.0	23810.4
3.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.2	34.9	695.5	3226.5	5675.0	5099.1	2838.0	1114.4	337.7	84.3	18.2	3.5	0.6	0.1	0.0	19128	
4.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.0	196.1	1354.3	3288.5	3857.5	2685.5	1275.2	455.1	130.9	31.9	6.9	1.3	0.2	0.0	13289.4	
5.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	51.0	498.4	1602.9	2372.7	2008.3	1126.0	463.6	150.9	41.0	9.7	2.1	0.4	0.1	8328.1	
6.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.2	12.6	167.0	690.3	1257.9	1268.6	825.9	386.8	140.8	42.2	10.9	2.5	0.5	0.1	4806.3	
7.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.0	52.1	270.1	594.4	703.2	524.9	276.7	111.7	36.7	10.2	2.5	0.6	0.1	2586.2	
8.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.7	15.4	97.9	255.9	350.6	296.9	174.6	77.6	27.7	8.4	2.2	0.5	0.1	1308.5	
9.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.2	4.3	33.2	101.9	159.9	152.2	99.2	48.3	18.7	6.1	1.7	0.4	0.1	626.2	
10.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.2	10.7	37.9	67.5	71.7	51.5	27.3	11.4	4.0	1.2	0.3	0.1	284.8	
11.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.3	3.3	13.3	26.6	31.4	24.7	14.2	6.4	2.4	0.7	0.2	0.1	123.6	
12.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	1.0	4.4	9.9	12.8	11.0	6.8	3.3	1.3	0.4	0.1	0.0	51.1	
13.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.3	1.4	3.5	5.0	4.6	3.1	1.6	0.7	0.2	0.1	0.0	20.5	
14.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.4	1.2	1.8	1.8	1.3	0.7	0.3	0.1	0.0	0.0	7.7	
15.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.4	0.6	0.7	0.5	0.3	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	2.8	
16.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.9	
sum	0	0	0	1.3	165.4	2091.2	9279.9	19921.8	24878.8	20869.9	12898.4	6244.9	2479	836.7	247.3	65.8	15.8	3.4	0.7	100000	

Figure 2. Wave conditions under which the sloshing model test was conducted (boxed with a bold border on NA scatter diagram)

2.3 Model Test Setup & Post Processing

The model tests were conducted at the sloshing test facility of Seoul National University. A hexapod-type motion platform was employed, capable of simulating six degrees of freedom (6DOF) ship motions, including surge, sway, heave, roll, pitch, and yaw. The tank model used in the experiments is a 1/50 scale replica of Tank No. 2 from Samsung Heavy Industries' 174K S-LNGC. Key geometric parameters of the model tank are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Dimensions of tank (model size)

	Dimensions (mm)
Length (l)	952
Breadth (b)	789
Height (h)	578
Upper chamfer height and breadth (c_1)	186
Lower chamfer height and breadth (c_2)	77

To minimize tank wall vibrations and ensure measurement accuracy, the model tank was fabricated using thick acrylic plates with a thickness ranging from 35 mm to 40 mm (Figure 3). While a number of previous studies have investigated the effects of different internal media on sloshing impact characteristics, this study utilized water and air due to their practicality and ease of handling in laboratory conditions.

Figure 3. Model tank setup(left) and sensor cluster(right) [9]

A total of 214 pressure sensors were installed inside the tank to measure sloshing-induced impact loads. To sufficiently capture localized pressure peaks caused by sloshing impacts, sensor clusters arranged in 3×3 or 4×4 grids were deployed at critical regions of the tank wall with 20kHz sampling frequency, as illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Sensor arrangement on the model tank [9]

2.4 Statistical Post-processing

To evaluate the probabilistic behavior of sloshing impacts, statistical post-processing was performed on the measured pressure signals. A Peak-Over-Threshold (POT) method was employed to extract representative peak events from the time series data. Specifically, within each 0.2-second time window, the highest peak that crossed a predefined threshold of 2.5 kPa—both upward and downward—was selected as a valid sloshing event. This approach effectively isolates high magnitude impacts while suppressing minor fluctuations or noise.

The POT method was flexibly applied either to each pressure sensor individually or grouped by cluster panel, or all sensor channels depending on the analysis objective. Unless otherwise noted, this study focuses on the results based on peak extraction across all channels collectively.

The extracted pressure peaks were sorted by magnitude and fitted to a three-parameter Weibull distribution, which was used to statistically model the exceedance probability of sloshing loads. The cumulative distribution function (CDF) of this distribution is expressed as:

$$F(x) = 1 - \left[- \left(\frac{x - \delta}{\beta} \right)^{\gamma} \right] \quad \text{for } x > \delta \quad (2)$$

where δ is the location parameter, β is the scale parameter, and γ is the shape parameter. This distribution enables accurate tail fitting of extreme pressure events, which is critical for predicting design sloshing loads in a long-term probabilistic framework. As a fitting method, Method of moment was applied. Statistical post-processing was conducted for each test condition, and Weibull-fitted parameters have been established for every operational scenario.

3 Establishing Global Wave Scatter Data for Liquefied Gas Carrier

3.1 Pre-processing of AIS Data for Gas Carrier Operations

The North Atlantic wave scatter diagram, as presented in IACS Recommendation No. 34, is one of the most widely adopted environmental representations in marine design. This dataset is frequently used in sloshing load analyses as a standard basis for estimating design conditions. However, most existing studies rely exclusively on this North Atlantic (NA) scatter diagram, while sloshing-related research incorporating wave climates from other ocean regions remains relatively limited [21]. Applications of such region-specific wave scatter diagrams within a long-term probabilistic sloshing assessment framework are even more scarce in the literature, despite the increasing relevance of performance-based and route-specific design approaches.

Since 2018, Korean Register (KR) has been collecting AIS data from classed vessels and utilizing this information to support a wide range of services, including operational profile analysis and fuel consumption evaluation. Leveraging this AIS dataset, a global shipping route analysis was conducted for liquefied gas carriers, with the objective of deriving route-specific wave scatter data tailored to LNG vessel operations.

AIS information from LNG carriers was utilized to identify representative sailing routes and their corresponding environmental exposure. These vessel trajectories were then combined with long-term hindcast wave data to construct detailed, probabilistically weighted wave scatter tables. In particular, the ERA5 reanalysis dataset was employed to provide high-resolution wave statistics along each route [22]. The ERA5 archive offers hourly records of significant wave height and wave period globally from 1979 to the present, enabling the derivation of joint distributions of sea states that realistically represent the long-term operational environment experienced by LNG carriers.

To ensure that the resulting wave scatter data reflects typical ocean-going conditions, a filtering process was applied to the raw AIS dataset. This step was necessary to exclude observations not representative of deep-sea operations—such as port stays, inland navigation, or coastal maneuvering—which may introduce bias in environmental statistics. The filtering criteria, summarized in Table 2, were applied to a total of 2,762,395 AIS observations, resulting in 955,957 valid offshore records. This corresponds to approximately 34.6% of the initial dataset, forming a robust basis for constructing realistic, route-specific scatter diagrams for LNG carrier operations.

It should be noted, however, that some uncertainties remain. The ERA5 reanalysis provides global coverage at relatively coarse spatial and temporal resolution, and may smooth local extremes or underrepresent rapidly evolving sea states. Similarly, the AIS filtering criteria, while designed to remove non-representative records, inevitably involve that can affect the resulting route statistics. These limitations do not invalidate the derived scatter tables, but they should be recognized as potential sources of bias when interpreting the results.

Table 2. Details of AIS data filtering

Filter Step	Remained Data	Remaining Ratio
1. Raw data	2,762,395	100.0
2. Delete empty or unusual data	2,553,021	92.4
3. Delete in-port* condition	1,861,744	67.4
4. Delete data whose speed is lower than 5kn	1,417,945	51.3
5. Delete data where water depth is shallower than -200m	955,957	34.6

In-port condition: ['At anchor', 'Moored', 'Aground'] status of AIS data in the category of 'navigation status'.

3.2 Global Sea Usage Distribution

Figure 5 illustrates the global sea usage distribution of liquefied gas carriers, derived from AIS observations that remained after the filtering process described in Table 2. The map shows the number of AIS data points aggregated in spatial bins of $0.5^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$ (latitude \times longitude). The density of AIS observations is represented by a color gradient, where darker red tones correspond to higher traffic frequencies on a logarithmic scale.

The figure clearly reveals the dominant sailing routes of liquefied gas carriers across the globe. High-density corridors are observed in the North Pacific, connecting East Asia to North America; the Indian Ocean and Middle East, linking Qatar and other major exporting terminals to Southeast Asia and Europe; and the Atlantic routes between the Gulf of Mexico, the Caribbean, and European import terminals. Additionally, significant traffic is concentrated along strategic chokepoints such as the Strait of Hormuz, the Suez Canal, and the Strait of Malacca.

To further quantify the geographic distribution of LNG carrier operations, the AIS data were categorized according to major oceanic regions. The resulting proportions are summarized in Table 3. Among these, the North Pacific Ocean accounted for the highest share at 39.7%, followed by the North Atlantic Ocean at 22.4%, and the Indian Ocean at 15.7%. Other regions, including South East Asia (8.9%) and the South Atlantic (6.1%), also showed notable activity. The classification of ocean regions used in this study is simplified and illustrated in Figure 6. The criteria for this classification were defined in a previous study by [23]. LNG carriers primarily operate on transoceanic routes outside the North Atlantic, emphasizing the need to consider regional wave environments for long-term sloshing load assessments instead of relying solely on the North Atlantic scatter diagram.

Figure 5. Contour plot of sea usage of liquefied gas carriers (KR classed ship)

Table 3. AIS data distribution by ocean

Ocean	Percentage
North Atlantic Ocean	22.4
South Atlantic Ocean	6.1
North Pacific Ocean	39.7
South Pacific Ocean	2.5
Indian Ocean	15.7
South East Asia	8.9
Mediterranean Ocean	3.1
Oceania	1.6

Figure 6. Classification of ocean regions

3.3 Construction of Global Route-Specific Wave Scatter Diagram

Based on the AIS-derived route analysis, a global wave scatter diagram representative of LNG carrier operations was constructed, as shown in Figure 7. This diagram was developed by coupling vessel trajectories with ERA5 hindcast wave data to statistically characterize the wave environment typically encountered along actual LNG shipping routes. Similar to the North Atlantic (NA) scatter diagram presented earlier in Figure 2, the sea states corresponding to sloshing model test conditions are indicated with bold-bordered boxes. To ensure a consistent basis for comparison with the NA dataset, the mean zero-crossing period T_z was estimated from the ERA5 mean wave period T_{0m1} using the empirical formulation provided in [19].

A comparison between the global and NA scatter diagrams reveals that the model test conditions are generally well represented in both, confirming the validity of applying long-term sloshing analysis using the global route-specific scatter. However, the two datasets exhibit notable differences in environmental characteristics, as highlighted in Figure 8. The global scatter shows a higher probability of encountering low to moderate wave heights, with significantly reduced exposure to sea states exceeding 3–4 meters. In contrast, the NA scatter exhibits a greater likelihood of severe wave conditions.

In terms of wave periods, both distributions show Gaussian-like shapes, but with distinct modal values. The NA scatter peaks around 8–9 seconds, while the global scatter shows the highest probability in the 6–7 second range. This difference is consistent with the observation that longer wave periods tend to be associated with higher sea states, suggesting that LNG carriers on global routes more frequently experience shorter, milder wave conditions. These findings further support the need for regionally tailored wave scatter diagrams when evaluating sloshing loads, particularly in a long-term probabilistic framework.

$$T_{0m1} = 1.33(0.7757 + 0.0965\sqrt{\gamma} - 0.0144\gamma)T_z \quad (3)$$

HS Tz	0.5	1.5	2.5	3.5	4.5	5.5	6.5	7.5	8.5	9.5	10.5	11.5	12.5	13.5	14.5	15.5	16.5	17.5	18.5	sum
0.5	0.8	108.8	1453.2	4463.4	4593.8	3164.2	1974.5	973.9	354.9	94.9	21.7	4.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	17208.5
1.5	0.0	0.0	8.1	1226.3	5860.3	9954.1	11636.2	9838.5	6121.7	2777.4	855.3	164.2	15.7	1.4	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	48459.4
2.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.4	285.8	2898.8	6451.1	6424.9	4528.1	2404.1	948.4	280.7	53.0	7.9	0.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	24284.3
3.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.3	145.3	1367.7	2049.6	1488.9	959.4	507.2	190.6	47.8	9.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	6766.9
4.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.1	142.9	625.3	604.8	365.3	203.7	94.2	30.2	6.9	0.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2075.2
5.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	7.8	131.9	259.3	184.0	90.6	39.6	13.4	3.3	0.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	730.3
6.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.3	20.1	86.0	98.1	51.3	18.9	5.4	1.3	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	281.8
7.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.4	21.5	43.4	31.3	11.0	2.4	0.5	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	112.6
8.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.2	4.4	15.6	17.8	7.5	1.3	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	47.1
9.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.8	4.7	8.4	5.0	0.8	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	19.9
10.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	1.2	3.4	3.1	0.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	8.5
11.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.3	1.1	1.6	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.6
12.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.3	0.7	0.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.4
13.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.5
14.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1
15.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
16.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
sum	0.8	108.8	1461.3	5690.1	10740.2	16163.5	21580.7	20066.8	13470.7	6948.7	2740.6	821.3	172.4	30.6	3.3	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	10000.0

Figure 7. Scatter diagram of liquefied gas carrier (KR classed ship)

Figure 8. Comparison of sea state: North Atlantic sea vs. global route – liquified gas carrier (KR classed ship)

3.4 Analysis of Relative Wave Headings in LNG Carrier Operations

Unlike traditional wave scatter diagrams that lack directional exposure data, the global scatter developed in this study allows for a thorough analysis of operational conditions. Because the wave scatter was developed by synchronizing real-world AIS trajectories with ERA5 hindcast wave data, it also allows for the extraction of statistical distributions for relative wave headings encountered by LNG carriers. These heading statistics, unavailable in standard design datasets, are visualized in Figure 9.

The data shows that when significant wave height is between 1 m and 2 m, there is a higher chance of encountering beam sea conditions at headings of 90° and 270° . However, this trend is not prominent at higher wave heights, and no systematic shift in heading preference is observed as wave severity increases. Overall, when aggregated over all wave height intervals, the relative wave heading distribution is nearly uniform.

This implies that, in practice, LNG carriers do not significantly alter their course based on wave direction, even in more severe sea states. Such a finding supports the assumption of even probability for relative wave headings in long-term sloshing analyses, and further highlights the value of AIS-informed environmental modeling in capturing realistic operational exposures.

Figure 9. Scatter diagram of liquified gas carrier (KR classed ship)

4 Estimation of Long-term Probability for Sloshing Load

4.1 Comparison of Long-term Sloshing Load Probabilities under Different Wave Climates

To quantify the impact of sea state variability on long-term sloshing loads, probabilistic load distributions were constructed using two different wave scatter datasets: the conventional North Atlantic (NA) scatter and the global route-based scatter specifically derived for liquefied gas carriers. In this analysis, the occurrence probabilities of cargo filling levels and relative wave headings were kept constant. Only the frequency of each sea state, which is defined by a combination of significant wave height H_s and zero-crossing period T_z , was varied according to the respective scatter diagrams. Figure 10 shows the long-term exceedance probabilities of sloshing loads. The thick black curve represents the aggregate across all conditions, while the thin grey curves show the contributions from individual conditions; the three most influential conditions are highlighted in color. By construction, the sum of the thin curves equals the thick black curve.

It is important to note that the sloshing load data used in both cases were identical and were measured through the same set of model tests. These loads were normalized by the hydrostatic pressure corresponding to the tank height, which allows for a direct comparison of design load levels across different wave environments. To facilitate this comparison, exceedance lines corresponding to a 25-year return period were added to the figure. These lines represent the most probable maximum (MPM) sloshing load under each wave climate.

The results show that the global route-based scatter yields a design load that is approximately 10 percent lower than the NA-based scatter, when assessed in terms of MPM value for the 25-year return period. Although this reduction may appear relatively small, especially in light of the fact that the global scatter shows less than half the probability of encountering extreme wave heights, it aligns with the known characteristics of long-term probabilistic load estimation.

As discussed in previous studies [9], long-term sloshing loads are not governed solely by extreme wave events. Rather, sea states that are moderate in severity but occur frequently make a significant contribution to the cumulative exceedance probability. This characteristic is illustrated in Figure 10, where the cumulative probability line includes annotations highlighting the sea states that contribute most substantially to the total long-term sloshing load. These findings underscore the importance of accounting for both the frequency and severity of environmental conditions. They also suggest that relying exclusively on the NA scatter may lead to conservative design outcomes that do not reflect actual LNG carrier operating conditions.

Figure 10. Exceedance probability of sloshing load

Table 4. Comparison of extreme wave heights and design sloshing loads : North Atlantic vs. global route – gas carrier

	North Atlantic	Global route – gas carrier
Extreme wave height – 25yrs return period	15.3m	11.3m
Sloshing load – 25yrs return period	42.4	37.5

4.2 Contribution Analysis of Sea States in Long-term Sloshing Load Estimation

In the previous section, long-term design sloshing loads were compared using two different wave scatter datasets: the conventional North Atlantic (NA) scatter and a global route-based scatter tailored to liquefied gas carriers. The analysis revealed a clear difference in the resulting design loads, with the global scatter yielding a lower value. To further investigate this observation, this section analyzes the contribution of individual sea states to the exceedance probability corresponding to the 25-year return period. The design load thresholds used in this analysis are 42.4 for the NA scatter and 37.5 for the global scatter. For each dataset, the contribution of every sea state—defined by the combination of significant wave height H_s , zero-crossing period T_z , and relative wave heading—was calculated. The results are summarized in Figures 11 and 12. The total of all contributions matches the cumulative exceedance probability associated with the 25-year return level.

This approach allows for the identification of specific sea state conditions that most significantly influence the long-term sloshing response. The findings offer insights into the relative importance of rare but severe conditions compared to more moderate yet frequently occurring sea states. When observing the overall trends, there was no clear or consistent pattern of dominant sea states solely based on wave dataset or relative wave heading. For example, a condition such as a " $\beta = 90^\circ, H_s = 2.5m, T_z = 8.5s$ " condition showed a high contribution in both datasets. In contrast, the condition with a " $\beta = 135^\circ, H_s = 10.5m, T_z = 13.5s$ " condition had a significant contribution only in the NA dataset. This is because the probability of encountering wave heights above 10 meters in the global route dataset is extremely low. As a result, even if sloshing loads under such conditions are high, their influence on the long-term exceedance probability remains minimal. Conversely, in the global dataset, a condition with a relative heading " $\beta = 135^\circ, H_s = 1.5m, T_z = 5.5s$ " was found to contribute significantly to the long-term load, despite the low wave height. This is attributed to its relatively high frequency of occurrence in actual operations. These observations suggest that common conditions, even if not severe, significantly impact design loads.

Such findings emphasize the importance of accurately representing real-world operational exposure when conducting long-term sloshing assessments. Incorporating route-specific wave scatter data into the evaluation process enhances the fidelity of probabilistic analyses and reduces the risk of overly conservative or non-representative design decisions.

Figure 11. Contribution of each weather condition to long-term probability of sloshing load, North Atlantic sea

Figure 12. Contribution of each weather condition to long-term probability of sloshing load, Global route – gas carrier

5 Conclusion

This study presented a comprehensive investigation into the impact of wave scatter characteristics on the long-term estimation of sloshing loads for LNG cargo containment systems. Recognizing the limitations of conventional short-term analyses and the over-reliance on the North Atlantic (NA) wave scatter diagram, a global route-specific framework was developed by integrating AIS-based vessel trajectories with ERA5 hindcast wave data. This approach enabled the construction of wave scatter diagrams that more accurately reflect the operational environments of liquefied gas carriers.

Several key findings can be summarized as follows:

- When using the global route-based wave scatter, the 25-year return design sloshing load was approximately 10% lower than that derived from the NA scatter. This suggests that the NA-based approach may lead to overly conservative load estimates for vessels operating outside extreme environments.
- Contribution analysis revealed that long-term design loads are not solely governed by rare and severe sea states. Instead, moderately severe conditions with high frequencies of occurrence play a critical role in shaping the exceedance probability. This finding highlights the limitations of extreme-condition-focused testing and supports the need for frequency-weighted load assessment.
- The global scatter dataset, enabled by AIS synchronization, allowed for the inclusion of relative wave heading statistics. Although some extreme headings showed isolated influence under specific wave conditions, the overall contribution patterns did not exhibit a strong dependence on heading alone. This suggests that operational avoidance or maneuvering strategies have limited effect on sloshing exposure in practice.
- By matching sloshing model test data with wave scatter probabilities derived from realistic routing data, this study confirmed the applicability of long-term probabilistic methods for sloshing load estimation. The results support the use of this framework for performance-based design, particularly for non-IGC-regulated LNG vessels such as LNG bunkering ships.

Overall, the study demonstrates that incorporating realistic, route-specific environmental statistics into sloshing assessments can lead to more efficient and tailored structural design. It also reinforces the importance of expanding the use of long-term analysis methodologies within the broader context of LNG shipping operations and cryogenic cargo containment safety.

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